

Hybrid Work and Sustainable Employment: A Study on Female Employees in Türkiye¹

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Abstract

In recent years, hybrid working systems have emerged as a transformative development in the structure of modern work. However, most existing research has primarily examined the economic advantages of hybrid work for organizations often overlooking its broader societal impacts, particularly those concerning women's employment. The broader implications of hybrid work across different cultural and social contexts also remain insufficiently explored. This gap has recently been highlighted by Shore et al. (2025) Accordingly, this research aimed to explore how hybrid work affects the well-being, work-life balance, and organizational commitment of female workers within the context of Türkiye. A structured survey which consists of five sections: demographic questions; "Hybrid Working Evaluation Form" developed by Yosunkaya (2023); "Organizational Commitment Scale" developed by Allen & Meyer (1990); "Employee Well-being Scale" developed by Pradhan & Hati (2022) and "Work-Life Balance Scale"

developed by Apaydın (2011) designed. Hofstede's (2025) country map was used to evaluate findings in the cultural context. 384 females participated to this research who are working in banking industry. They were chosen based on purposive sampling. Findings demonstrated that hybrid work environment positively affecting well-being however, negatively affecting work-life balance. This study further reveals that while well-being is positively influencing; work-life balance is negatively influencing organizational commitment. This underscores the importance of strategy and culture-based hybrid work policies to not only promote well-being but also prevent work-life imbalances.

Keywords: Hybrid Work, Employee Well-Being, Work-Life Balance, Organizational Commitment, Sustainability.

JEL Codes: Q01, D23, J01, M14

¹This article is derived from a study originally presented at the IX. ASC 2025 Spring Congress (May 15–18, 2025), hosted by İstanbul Gedik University in İstanbul, Türkiye, and has been substantially revised to meet the academic and editorial standards required for publication.

Citation: Al, B. (2025). Hybrid Work and Sustainable Employment: A Study on Female Employees in Türkiye. *Researches on Multidisciplinary Approaches (Romaya Journal)*, 5(SI-IXASC2025): 177-200.

1. Introduction

In recent years, hybrid working systems have emerged as a transformative development in the structure of modern work. However, most existing research has primarily examined the economic advantages of hybrid work for organizations often overlooking its wider societal impacts, particularly those concerning women's employment. Implications of hybrid work across different cultural and social contexts also remain insufficiently explored. In fact, most empirical research continues to be concentrated in Western contexts, where individualistic cultural values, low power distance, and low uncertainty avoidance dominate workplace dynamics (Setiyono et al., 2024). However, in these studies, the focus has largely remained on understanding hybrid work effect on employees' well-being and productivity within these cultural frameworks, leaving significant questions unanswered regarding how such work models function in non-Western societies, where workplace dynamics are shaped by distinct cultural, institutional, and social frameworks. This gap has recently been highlighted by Shore et al. (2025) and the authors called for future research to explore how employee-organization relationships and employee health outcomes are influenced by evolving work arrangements, particularly in non-Western contexts where cultural values and organizational expectations may diverge significantly from those prevalent in the West. In fact, hybrid work has demonstrated potential well-being benefits for certain groups such as working parents, disabled employees, female and disadvantaged individuals however, these findings are predominantly drawn from Western labor markets, which diminishes their generalizability across different cultural landscapes (Shore et al., 2025).

To respond to the identified research gaps, the present study aims to go beyond examining the direct associations between hybrid work and employee outcomes by investigating how and through which mechanisms hybrid work influences organizational commitment. Specifically, the study adopts a mediation-based approach to explore the dual roles of employee well-being and work-life balance as underlying explanatory variables. By drawing on the literature, the study integrates theoretical insights into a structured empirical model. Furthermore, by applying Baron and Kenny's (1986) mediation framework along with bootstrapped structural equation modeling, the research seeks to uncover not only whether hybrid work influences commitment, but also through which psychological and relational pathways these effects occur. In addition, this study proposes a context-sensitive conceptual model that incorporates Hofstede's cultural dimensions to interpret how national values such as high power distance, low individualism, and strong uncertainty avoidance may shape the effectiveness and perception of hybrid work systems. Through this multidimen-

sional and culturally informed design, the research aims to contribute a novel and empirically grounded framework to the hybrid work literature, particularly within underrepresented non-Western contexts.

Accordingly, exploring hybrid work effect on the well-being, work-life balance, and organizational commitment of female workers within the context of Türkiye has been determined as the aim of this study. Türkiye was chosen for several reasons. First of all, it is a non-Western culture representor. Secondly, in Türkiye, women are culturally referred as mothers rather than workers. This can be seen in the country's workforce structure. In fact, according to the Turkish Statistical Institute (2024) (TÜİK (Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu), 2024) the overall employment rate for individuals aged 15 and above stands at 47.5%. This figure diverges sharply by gender: 30.4% for women and 65.0% for men, indicating the existence of a significant gender gap in workforce participation, with the female employment rate being nearly half that of men. Another reason for selecting Türkiye is related to the current economic needs of the country. As a developing economy currently facing economic challenges, increasing female participation in the workforce remains a critical challenge for Türkiye. Indeed, studies indicate that increasing women's labor force participation directly contributes to economic growth and long-term economic sustainability (Vasconez Rodriguez, 2017). In fact, one of the latest study's conducted in Türkiye indicated that a 0.12% increase in economic growth is observed if a 1% increase in women's labor force participation is achieved (Çiğdem et al., 2023), making the country a highly relevant context for this research.

Accordingly, this research aims to produce evidence-based insights that can guide the development of gender-sensitive and actionable policies in hybrid work environments, making it possible for the country to achieve more inclusive and resilient workforce structures and overall sustainable economic development. The present research's results also provide a good example for countries that have similar cultures to Türkiye, in which women's participation in the workforce are low and may offer as a key factor to achieve sustainable development. This research also provides a good example for countries that have similar cultures to Türkiye, in which women's participation in the workforce are low and may offer valuable insights for sustainable development. In this perspective, the present research contributes not only to the academic understanding of hybrid work arrangements but also to the broader conversation on sustainable workforce engagement, gender equality, and social inclusion. Moreover, this study enriches established theoretical frameworks by offering a culture-based hybrid working model that increases the organizational commitment that makes it also valuable for business and academic world.

2. Theoretical Background and Formulation of Hypotheses

In this part of the research, existing studies in the literature were examined and hypotheses were created.

2.1. Hybrid Working

Although no universally accepted definition of hybrid work exists (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025), it is generally described as a work arrangement that integrates remote work with traditional office-based work, offering employees and organizations greater flexibility in structuring work processes (Shao et al., 2024). Hybrid work came into life in reaction to the changing demands of the modern workforce (Claes et al., 2023), challenges faced by the world because of the pandemic, and energy saving efforts of companies to become greener (Andriani, 2023).

Mortensen & Haas (2021) evaluated this working model in terms of its advantages compared to remote and office-based systems. According to them, hybrid working is defined as an effective system that offers benefits such as reducing commuting time, increasing flexibility and providing cost optimization to companies, as well as improved coordination and team creativity through the partial continuation of face-to-face work (Mortensen & Haas, 2021).

It is possible to say that hybrid working systems offer benefits from a wide perspective, from employees to businesses, and from businesses to sustainability (Andriani, 2023). From the employees' perspective, research shows that hybrid work is closely linked to enhanced work-life balance, reduced stress levels, and improved job satisfaction (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025). Similarly, hybrid working systems increase employees' control over their work, improving their psychological well-being and reducing work-related anxiety, thus helping to develop a more adaptive and inclusive workplace culture (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025). In addition, by allowing employees to customize their schedules, hybrid work models promote greater job satisfaction and organizational commitment, contributing to the overall sustainability of businesses (Bekele et al., 2024).

From a business perspective, hybrid work systems offer significant contributions to organizations. In fact, hybrid work contributes to the economic sustainability of businesses by reducing costs, enhancing employee productivity, maximizing business efficiency and supporting labor market inclusivity (Xie et al., 2025). Indeed, research on the subject shows that organizations adopting hybrid models have reported lower turnover rates, higher employee engagement, and improved talent retention (Brundtland, 2018). In addition, hybrid working reduces the need for office space, allowing businesses to reduce rental costs and energy costs, operate with an optimi-

zed workforce, and attract talent from a wider geographical area (Mortensen & Haas, 2021).

From a sustainability perspective, the hybrid work system provides benefits in three main categories: economic, social, and environmental. In this context, increasing workforce resilience, operational efficiency, and resource optimization contribute to sustainable economic development; while ensuring equitable, inclusive, and supportive workplaces that foster employee well-being, diversity, and long-term professional engagement contribute to social sustainability (Andriani, 2023). Reducing carbon emissions, optimizing resource consumption, and minimizing the ecological footprint of corporate operations are among the key contributions the hybrid work system makes to environmental sustainability (Andriani, 2023).

From a gendered perspective, hybrid working systems offer a meaningful opportunity to strengthen women's participation in the workforce and promote gender equality on a broader scale (Elsawy & Youssef, 2023). Indeed, one of the system's important features is its promotion of gender equality (OECD, 2017). For female employees, the system offers a unique opportunity to address long-standing gender disparities in the labor market. Historically, rigid office structures and inflexible working hours have had extremely negative effects on women, particularly those who undertake caregiving and household responsibilities (OECD, 2017) and in economies where cultural and societal expectations create barriers to full-time employment (Elsawy & Youssef, 2023). The OECD (2017) report shows that female workers experience more work-life conflict compared to male workers which causes career stagnation, higher burnout rates, and an increased likelihood of exiting the workforce. A hybrid working system can help reduce these problems. As a result, they can be better positioned to progress into leadership roles without sacrificing personal obligations.

When examined from the perspective of inclusivity, increased female participation in the workforce due to hybrid working systems directly supports at least nine of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2025). In this regard, hybrid work should not be viewed solely as a flexible employment arrangement, but rather as a strategic enabler of social inclusion (Caragnano, 2023), a mechanism for reducing inequality (Vasconez Rodriguez, 2017), and a pathway toward the economic empowerment of women (Elsawy & Youssef, 2023).

Although the hybrid working model offers clear and tangible benefits, it also brings with it several challenges that businesses should consider (Tenderis & Kazdal, 2023). In fact, Hybrid work arrangements inherently differ from fully remote or entirely on-site models, presenting a unique set of challenges (Claes et al., 2023). Claes et al. (2023) identify four major

challenging features of the hybrid working system. According to Claes et al. (2023), the first challenge arises from the loss of boundaries between professional and personal responsibilities (boundarylessness), which makes it difficult to disengage from work. Multitasking is another challenging feature proposed by Claes et al. (2023), as hybrid work often requires employees to manage multiple work tasks simultaneously within the same timeframe, leading to a constant need to prioritize competing responsibilities. Differing from remote workers, many hybrid workers lack a separate place to work in their homes, which makes them more vulnerable to non-work-related interruptions (Vartiainen & Vanharanta, 2023). This is stated by Claes et al. (2023) as a third challenging feature of hybrid working, as it leads to decreased concentration on work and leads to decreased overall performance. A final challenging feature is stated by Claes et al. (2023) as the “demand for continuous learning”. In this context, Xie et al. (2019) claimed that this working system requires a continuous adaptation of new technologies and requires employees to update their skills to stay competitive in a rapidly evolving workplace. Indeed, hybrid working system can negatively affect team harmony and employee loyalty (Setiyono et al., 2024). In addition, a hybrid working system may diminish the borders associated with work and individual tasks. This can cause employees to work beyond standard working hours, potentially leading to burnout (Setiyono et al., 2024).

The hybrid work system can also trigger psychological and behavioral difficulties that can cause disruptions in career development, decrease workplace commitment, and complicate the management of personal responsibilities (Kinsman et al., 2024). For example, managers may unknowingly prefer employees with whom they interact more frequently face-to-face, potentially leading to biases in promotion and career development processes (Kinsman et al., 2024). Similarly, communication gaps may occur between teams working remotely and those working in the office, weakening collaboration and the flow of information, which in turn can lead to a decrease in workplace engagement (Tenderis & Kazdal, 2023). Again, this working system can cause distraction and stress due to factors such as high noise levels and lack of private space in the home environment, potentially leading to mental fatigue, while frequent requests for information sharing may further interrupt workflow and make it more challenging to manage personal responsibilities (Kinsman et al., 2024). Finally, ensuring the security of digital infrastructure is of great importance in a hybrid working system, as the risk of a data security breach increases in this environment. These challenges clearly reveal the need for policies structured to maximize the advantages of hybrid working while minimizing its negative effects (Tenderis & Kazdal, 2023).

Given the complex and context-dependent nature of hybrid work experiences, cultural values play a critical role in shaping how such arrangements are perceived and managed by employees. In Western cultures, hybrid work tends to strengthen well-being and commitment through enhanced autonomy and flexibility. In contrast, in Eastern cultures, these same elements may increase job demands, unless culturally sensitive leadership and structured organizational support are in place to provide clarity and mitigate uncertainty (Başar, 2024). In Western cultures, characterized by low power distance, high individualism, and low uncertainty avoidance, autonomy and flexibility, which are central to hybrid work models, are generally perceived as positive job resources. Employees in these contexts are accustomed to making independent decisions, managing their own schedules, and thriving in environments that offer discretion over work processes. Consequently, autonomy fosters a sense of control, enhancing well-being and facilitating work-life balance. Flexibility, similarly, enables individuals to manage both professional and personal responsibilities effectively, reducing role conflict and increasing satisfaction (Yosunkaya, 2023).

However, in Eastern cultures such as Türkiye, which exhibit high power distance, high uncertainty avoidance, and collectivism, the perception of these same work characteristics shifts. In these settings, autonomy may no longer function as a resource but rather transform into a demand. The hierarchical nature of high-power distance societies emphasizes top-down decision-making, where employees are more comfortable receiving direct instructions from their superiors. When autonomy is granted without structured guidance, it can create ambiguity and stress, particularly in cultures where uncertainty avoidance is strong and individuals seek clear rules and predictable environments. Therefore, flexibility in hybrid work settings, which inherently introduces variability in work schedules and responsibilities, might also be perceived as an additional source of uncertainty rather than a benefit (Başar, 2024).

The collectivist orientation further complicates the reception of hybrid work. In collectivist cultures, face-to-face interactions, group cohesion, and shared decision-making are essential components of workplace dynamics (Hofstede et al., 2010). Hybrid work, by reducing physical presence and increasing remote interactions, can inadvertently weaken social bonds, erode trust, and disrupt team dynamics. As a result, employees may experience diminished well-being and reduced work-life balance, particularly when organizational support systems are insufficient to bridge these gaps. Interestingly, cultural factors can also mitigate these negative outcomes under certain conditions. For instance, the femininity dimension, which emphasizes quality of life, care, and cooperation, can enhance the perception

of job resources, even in more hierarchical cultures (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025). In societies where femininity is stronger, supportive leadership, structured policies, and psychological safety can counterbalance the stress induced by high demands, fostering well-being and enhancing organizational commitment. Considering these cultural differences will be base for the hypothesis development which will be done in the next section.

2.2. Hybrid Work and Work-Life Balance

A critical longstanding issue which has been questioned since the beginning of working life has been how employees achieve work-life balance, and how this affects their health and performance. Today, this issue is generally explained by the Work-Family Conflict (WFC) Theory (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985) which is related to the idea that employees have both work and home lives, and that they have their own set of responsibilities in each of these lives (Sohal & Sharma, 2024). For example, a female employee can be a mother at home, fulfilling her maternal responsibilities, while simultaneously serving as a manager at work with administrative duties. Since these two responsibilities are carried out concurrently, they can sometimes lead to conflicts over shared resources such as energy and attention (Sohal & Sharma, 2024).

Work-Family Conflict occurs in two ways. The first of these emerges as work life interference with family life (WIF). For example, a mother's inability to attend her child's school activities due to long working hours is an example of WIF. Family life interference with work life (FIW) is exact opposite of WIF and constitutes the second dimension of Work-Family Conflict. For example, a mother being late for work due to her child's illness is an example of FIW. Both ways negatively impact the mental and physical health of individuals, thereby decreasing organizational performance and employee commitment while increasing turnover rates.

When studies are surveyed, the issues that trigger work-life conflict the most are workload, time pressure, and gender roles, with the resulting effects including stress, depression, and low life satisfaction (Xie et al., 2025). Women are more likely than men to experience work-life conflict, which increases their risk of career stagnation, burnout, and eventual withdrawal from the labor force (OECD, 2017). Hybrid work may help reduce these risks by allowing women to handle both their professional and individual tasks more effectively. In fact, in contrast to traditional work structures, technological developments and flexible working styles in the modern business world continue to trigger conflict, however they create opportunities for balance (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025). Recent studies have shown that hybrid work

arrangements play an effective role in maintaining work-life balance (Mishra & Bharti, 2024). This effectiveness stems from features such as the flexibility and autonomy that hybrid work systems provide employees in creating their own work schedules and in reducing the time spent commuting (Liu, 2022). In this context, it has been stated that hybrid work reduces stress caused by work-life balance and increases job satisfaction (Liu, 2022). In addition, other studies have shown that granting employees more autonomy in determining their work arrangements through the hybrid work system increases psychological well-being, reduces work-related anxiety, and promotes a more harmonious, inclusive workplace culture (Lauring & Jonasson, 2025). Likewise, Liu (2022) indicated that hybrid working systems increase productivity, reduces stress, and strengthen employee commitment to their organization. Andriani (2023) on the other hand, found that hybrid working combined the advantages of remote and office-based working, allowing female managers to have more control over their schedules and maintain their professional commitment.

A similar study conducted by Yosunkaya (2023) with 400 people working in hybrid arrangements in Türkiye also supported these findings. Yosunkaya (2023) found that 86.8% of participants were satisfied with hybrid working and supported making the model permanent. However, despite its advantages, and in contrast to the findings of Andriani (2023), a significant portion of participants (66%) expressed concerns about the elimination of specific working hours. Participants also reported that they felt pressured to be constantly accessible outside of standard working hours (Yosunkaya, 2023). According to Yosunkaya (2023), this situation leads to negative consequences such as increased stress levels and work-family conflict. At this point, unresolved conflicts between work and personal responsibilities have been found to create dissatisfaction in the workplace and intention to leave one's job (Yosunkaya, 2023).

Several other studies further report that hybrid work has negative effects, such as da Silva et al. (2022). According to their findings, hybrid work systems offer flexibility to employees, but also present several challenges especially for female managers in terms of career visibility and promotion opportunities. However, some studies also showed that the hybrid model can create a sense of having to be constantly available among employees, leading to additional stress, diminishing the anticipated benefits of flexibility (Selvaraju, 2024).

According to Selvaraju (2024), in order to address the challenges that hybrid work system may create, institutions need to develop policies to maintain work-life balance, promote practices that will reduce the feeling of constant connection, and support a corporate culture that values employee well-being

as much as professional performance. In support of Selvaraju (2024), Setiyono et al. (2024) also suggested that the success of an effective hybrid working system that promotes better work-life balance largely relates to how organizations integrate technology, leadership strategies, and well-structured policy practices. In other words, employees' work-life balance experiences are shaped by the overall work-family culture within organizations. Organizational environments that prioritize flexibility and employee well-being reduce work-family conflict and increase job satisfaction (Liu, 2022). Accordingly, it has been stated that when effectively implemented, hybrid work systems increase employee well-being, lower turnover rates, and contribute to the formation of a more committed and resilient workforce (Setiyono et al., 2024).

Empirical findings reveal that hybrid working systems have complex consequences on work-life conflict, and that achieving positive outcomes depends on organizational cultures supported by well-structured hybrid work. It is also clear from the findings of other studies that different country settings created different results and study conducted in Türkiye indicated that unclear working hours raised by the hybrid working led to stress in which the employees felt pressured to be constantly accessible outside of standard working hours (Yosunkaya, 2023). Thus, this situation has led to negative consequences such as increased stress levels and work-family conflict. Based on this, the first hypothesis for this study is set as "hybrid work has a negative effect on work-life balance" (H1).

Research has also shown that job satisfaction and organizational commitment are positively affected by an increased work-life balance through the hybrid work system (Bekele et al., 2024). The study by Saritha & Akthar (2024) also revealed similar results. Accordingly, they found that organizations adopting a hybrid model experience lower employee turnover rates and higher employee commitment (Saritha & Akthar, 2024). In support of these results, Brundtland (2018) also stated that the hybrid work system, which he argued is of critical importance in building a sustainable economic structure, also has positive effects on retaining talented employees. Nevertheless, some studies also suggested that increased flexibility and autonomy offered by the hybrid working systems may lead to negative outcomes such as work intensification, boundary blurring, or professional isolation, especially in non-Western or high-context cultures (Başar, 2024). Başar's (2024) indication is done in the case of Türkiye and thus in this study it is expected that increased flexibility and autonomy offered by the hybrid working systems will lead to negative outcome and thus the second hypothesis is set as "work-life balance has a negative effect on employee commitment" (H2).

2.3. Hybrid Work and Employee Well-Being

Employee well-being is a critical pillar of workforce sustainability, influencing job performance, mental health, and overall organizational engagement (Din et al., 2025). Many studies have benefited from the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model to examine the topic of employee well-being (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

In simple terms, JD-R defends that factors affecting employee well-being in addition to employees' health, motivation, and performance, mostly arise from two sources: job demands and job resources (Dlouhy et al., 2024). Dlouhy et al. (2024) describe job demands as "job requirements," which include the physical, emotional, or cognitive effort required to carry out work tasks. They further add that the mentioned efforts are significantly related to stress and strain among employees. This is supported by Bhargavi (2025) who claim that job-related efforts are often perceived as an "excessive workload," leading to feelings of time pressure, and role ambiguity in employees. This, as a result, may lead to burnout, emotional exhaustion, and disengagement (Bhargavi, 2025). Other scholars such as da Silva et al. (2022) further support these arguments and claim that high job demands predict future burnout, which, in turn, increases the risk of depression. In fact, their study on teachers (da Silva et al., 2022) demonstrates that workload and time constraints negatively impact employees well-being. On the contrary, when job resources are considered, da Silva et al. (2022) define these as organizational, social, or personal assets that help employees achieve their work goals. These resources ultimately serve to decrease stress and improve well-being. Examples of these include autonomy, colleague support, job security, and career development opportunities. Empirical studies highlight that colleague support can lower the negative impact of job demands, enable higher motivation, and improve job satisfaction (Bhargavi, 2025). Similarly, research carried out among Belgian employees indicated that autonomy and a sense of competence, both personal assets, positively correlate with subjective well-being (Villiger & Hämmig, 2023). The same study also revealed that job demands have an adverse effect on well-being. da Silva et al. (2022) add that the intensity of job demands may vary depending on the level of resources available within the organization. Supporting the idea, Selvaraju (2024) argued that effective leadership, structured policies, and a supportive work culture can help reduce stressors and optimize the benefits offered by job resources. Research on Portuguese teachers (da Silva et al., 2022) and Swiss healthcare workers (Villiger & Hämmig, 2023) further supported this view.

The hybrid working system has been widely recog-

nized by recent studies such as Mortensen & Haas (2021) as a working model that can enhance employee well-being through decreasing stressors related to the workplace, offering greater autonomy over employees' work, and promoting a stronger sense of control over work dynamics. Studies have shown that providing employees with greater autonomy in choosing their work arrangements enhances psychological well-being and supports more adaptive workplace culture (Sun et al., 2025). Furthermore, the hybrid model reduces commuting-related stress, increases job satisfaction, and positively influences psychological resilience (Sun et al., 2025).

In this regard, Başar (2024) argue that if organizations aim to support the well-being of female managers, they must adopt hybrid working systems. However, Başar (2024) also added that fostering resilience at work and developing workplace policies sensitive to female specific needs is equally important when adopting hybrid working models. This is because, despite its identified benefits, hybrid working systems may also raise problems for women which can negatively impact their well-being. Bhargavi (2025) further supported the ideas of Başar (2024) and claimed that if hybrid work models fail to address gendered challenges such as leadership visibility, equitable career progression, and social support, they may increase stress and ultimately reduce female managers' long-term engagement in leadership roles. Data from OECD (2017) further underscores the persistence of these issues, with the report stating that without targeted policies which address such problems, hybrid work may risk increasing existing gender-based inequalities instead of supporting equality within workplaces.

Studies also indicate that women working remotely often experience increased pressure from household responsibilities, which increases tensions in their families as well as causing difficulties in maintaining productivity and professional visibility (Elsawy & Youssef, 2023). These problems may be exacerbated due to the social isolation created by working from home and thus contribute to elevated levels of stress and anxiety. As a result, the career sustainability of female employees is negatively affected (Başar, 2024). At this point the OECD (2017) report indicates that organizational support systems such as mental health resources, mentorship programs, and clear guidelines on work expectations decrease the aforementioned stressors and increase the effectiveness of hybrid working systems.

Further research highlights both the benefits and risks associated with working from home (WFH) and hybrid work models, particularly for women (Gorjifard & Crawford, 2021). Gorjifard & Crawford (2021) state that while the hybrid working system offers increased autonomy and flexibility for female workers, it also presents occupational health and safety concer-

ns. Specifically, women who are working from home are more subject to health and safety issues because of their domestic responsibilities. Additionally, the absence of a dedicated workspace at home leads to higher personal costs, as employees need to invest in a functional workstation to maintain productivity. This absence of a functional workstation also puts further pressure on women since they also need to catch-up with rapidly evolving workplace technologies (Gorjifard & Crawford, 2021).

It is understood from literature that especially non-western studies indicated negative outcomes. Nevertheless, this study focusses on banking employees where long working hours and high-pressure significantly exist. In addition, many banking general offices are in city centers which require long travelling time that increases stress and decreases well-being. Therefore, based on the sample of this study it is, in this manner, hypothesis that hybrid work will have a positive effect on the well-being of female employees (H3). Additionally, it is proposed that well-being functions in shaping organizational commitment and its effect on it will also be positive (H4).

2.4. Hybrid Work and Organizational Commitment

Many scholars apply the Three-Component Model of Commitment (TCM) to explain organizational commitment (Cassim et al., 2024). Developed by Allen & Meyer (1990), this model categorizes commitment into three fundamental dimensions: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. For female employees, organizational commitment is a critical factor not only for sustaining engagement and professional development but also for reducing turnover intentions, increasing job satisfaction, and supporting long-term leadership retention (Saritha & Akthar, 2024). However, Cassim et al. (2024) argue that hybrid working systems present both opportunities and challenges that can either strengthen or weaken female employees' commitment. This is backed by their empirical findings. Specifically, Cassim et al. (2024) conducted a study with 133 academic staff members at a private higher education institution applying the Three-Component Model (TCM). Their findings revealed that while both work-from-home (WFH) and hybrid working system created challenges for employees, their affective and normative commitment remained stable (Cassim et al., 2024). Nevertheless, as mentioned earlier, hybrid working systems alone do not eliminate gendered barriers to the career progression of female employees. Research indicates that women in hybrid settings often face challenges related to workplace visibility, unfair promotion decisions, and reduced access to leadership development

opportunities due to reduced in-office presence (OECD, 2017). Indeed, unless hybrid working systems are structured to actively promote leadership inclusivity and career development, they may fail to retain top female talent in managerial positions (Saritha & Akthar, 2024). Building on this perspective, studies indicate that hybrid work significantly influences organizational commitment in industries with highly flexible and technology-driven environments (Vidya Sri & Vasantha, 2024). A study investigating the effectiveness of hybrid work structures in IT companies examined two dimensions (1) the effectiveness of hybrid workplace models and (2) the determinants of organizational commitment (Vidya Sri & Vasantha, 2024). Their findings demonstrated that well-structured hybrid models enhance workers' engagement and long-standing commitment. This emphasizes that the success of hybrid work depends on strategic implementation, strong leadership and fair promotion opportunities (Vidya Sri & Vasantha, 2024). Based on their findings, Vidya Sri & Vasantha (2024) concluded that hybrid work policies should not only provide flexibility but should also address gender-specific barriers in leadership and career progression as without these structural supports, hybrid working systems carries the risk of increasing gender inequalities rather than reducing it. Further research conducted by Bhargavi (2025) highlights that organizations with strong mentorship programs, leadership development initiatives, and transparent promotion criteria are more successful in promoting long-term organizational commitment among female employees. Addressing these barriers requires a holistic approach, incorporating mentorship opportunities, structured leadership pathways, and transparent performance evaluations that ensure female managers are equally considered for career advancement in hybrid work settings.

However, an alternative viewpoint suggests that when employees achieve better work-life balance, they may feel less dependent on their organizations and thus less committed. This shift in career priorities could lead female employees who achieve sustainable work-life balance to prioritize personal fulfillment over long-term loyalty to an organization (Bhargavi, 2025). Another study by Marozva & Pelsler (2025) claimed that greater autonomy in hybrid settings may reduce employees' sense of belonging, potentially weakening their long-term organizational commitment.

It is clear from the literature that hybrid work has a positive influence on organizational commitment among female employees however, if it is introduced carefully. Therefore, in this study, it is hypothesized that hybrid work will have positive effect on organizational commitment (H5).

In the conceptual framework of this study, work-life balance is proposed as a key mediator linking hybrid

work to organizational commitment. The rationale stems from work-family interface theories which suggest that a harmonious balance between work and personal life can translate into positive work outcomes. Empirical research shows that improved work-life balance is associated with higher job satisfaction and stronger organizational commitment (Liu, 2022; Bhargavi, 2025). This means that when employees are able to fulfill both work and family responsibilities without conflict, they are more likely to develop loyalty and remain engaged with their organization. Hybrid work arrangements, by reducing commuting time and offering scheduling flexibility, have the potential to lessen work-family conflicts and thereby improve work-life balance. In turn, a better work-life balance should foster greater commitment to the organization, as employees experience less stress and more support in managing their twofold roles. Recent evidence supports this connection: for example, a study in Ghana's higher education sector found that work-life balance significantly mediated the relationship between flexible work arrangements and employee performance (Eshun & Segbenya, 2024), underscoring how critical balance is for translating flexible work benefits into positive outcomes. Conversely, if hybrid work blurs boundaries and extends work into personal time, it may erode work-life balance and diminish organizational commitment. Some scholars caution that in cultures with strong family obligations or "always-on" expectations, employees who achieve a comfortable work-life balance might become less dependent on their jobs, and thus less emotionally committed to their employers. Başar (2024), for instance, observed that in non-Western contexts the added autonomy from hybrid work can sometimes lead to boundary-blurring and professional isolation, reducing hybrid work's intended benefits. Given these inconsistent findings, this study treats the hybrid work-work-life balance-commitment linkage as an open empirical question. Therefore, in this study it is hypothesized that hybrid work will have a negative effect on the work-life balance and that work-life balance in turn will have a negative effect on organizational commitment (H6), potentially serving as a mediator of hybrid work's influence on commitment.

Employee well-being is another central mediator in this study, grounded in both the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory and organizational psychology research on employee attitudes. The JD-R model posits that job resources such as flexibility and autonomy can boost employee well-being by reducing job-related stress and fulfilling basic psychological needs (Liu, 2022). Hybrid work environments often introduce valuable resources, for example, greater autonomy over work location and schedule, and relief from the stressors of commuting. Recent studies have widely recognized hybrid work as a model that can enhance well-being by decreasing workplace

stressors and giving employees more control over their work dynamics. Sun et al. (2025) found that allowing employees to choose their work arrangements improved psychological well-being and even fostered a more adaptive workplace culture. Such enhancements in well-being are expected to translate into stronger organizational commitment. When employees feel healthier, less stressed, and more supported, they are likely to develop more positive attitudes toward their employer and exhibit higher affective commitment. This aligns with social exchange theory which suggests that organizations that care for and invest in employees' well-being may cultivate a sense of reciprocity, prompting employees to respond with loyalty and commitment. Prior research indicates that well-being is closely tied to engagement and retention, for instance, Din et al. (2025) report that initiatives improving employee psychological well-being also elevate engagement levels at work which relate to commitment. Conversely, if hybrid work arrangements fail to safeguard employee well-being, employees' attachment to the organization might suffer. As Bhargavi (2025) ar-

gued, hybrid models that neglect gender-specific challenges can increase stress and ultimately reduce women's long-term engagement in their roles. Therefore, the extent to which hybrid work boosts organizational commitment likely hinges on its impact on employee well-being. Together with the prior hypotheses, this yields a mediational expectation. Therefore, the last hypothesis in this study is set as "hybrid work will have a positive effect on organizational commitment through the mediating role of employee well-being" (H7).

3. Materials and Methods

The present research aims to explore how hybrid work affects the well-being, work-life balance, and organizational commitment of female workers within the context of Türkiye as non-Western culture representative for two main reasons. Following a positivist and deductive approach, the following research model (Figure 1), which consists of the study's hypotheses is formed:

Figure 1. Research Model

A structured survey designed to assess the experiences of female employees working in hybrid environments. A structured survey which consists of five sections: demographic questions; "Hybrid Working Evaluation Form" developed by Yosunkaya (2023); "Organizational Commitment Scale" developed by Allen & Meyer (1990); "Employee Well-being Scale" developed by Pradhan & Hati (2022) and "Work-Life Balance Scale" developed by Apaydin (2011) designed.

Yosunkaya's (2023) scale features 14 questions and is structured as a five-point Likert-type measure. Allen & Meyer's (1990) scale comprises 3 subdimensions and 18 questions and uses a five-point Likert scale. Pradhan & Hati's (2022) scale has 4 subdimensions and 31 questions and uses a five-point Likert scale. Apaydin's (2011) scale consists of 4 subdimensions and twenty questions and uses a five-point Likert scale. To assess the culture, Hofstede's (2025) country map was used. Following Figure 2 provides Hofstede's (2025) country map for Türkiye used in this study:

Figure 2. Cultural Dimensions of Türkiye

Source: Hofstede (2025)

This research was conducted among women working in a hybrid working system in the banking sector. The rationale behind selecting female employees working specifically in the banking sector is related to the study's focus on hybrid work, well-being, and work-life balance. The banking industry is known for its long working hours, high-performance expectations, and competitive environment which presents a relevant and high-pressure context to conduct this study. When looked at it, regardless of the working system such as hybrid working, remote working, or working in the office, the biggest problem faced by studies conducted in Türkiye is that the sample size cannot be determined because the number of employees is not included in official statistics (e.g. Yosunkaya, 2023). Yosunkaya (2023) stated in his study that the minimum sample size required for a research based on a population of 10000 at a 95% confidence level for quantitative-oriented social science research is 370, 381 for 50000, and 384 for 1000000. Based on this point, the number of women working in the banking sector was first determined within the scope of this research. According to the January 2025 report of the Banks Association of Türkiye, the number of women working in the banking sector in Türkiye is 96210. Accordingly, 384 samples were targeted in this study.

A purposive sampling approach was used to ensure that the sample consisted of female employees working in hybrid environments, aligning with the research objectives. Purposive sampling was selected as the primary method as the study specifically targets a defined group of professionals whose experiences with hybrid work directly relate to the research questions. However, given the constraints in accessing a broad range of female employees in hybrid roles, a convenience sampling approach was also applied during the data collection process. Participants were recruited through professional networks, LinkedIn, and corporate contacts, allowing for efficient access to relevant respondents while maintaining the study's focus on hybrid work experiences. Thus, the final sample consisted of 384 female employees who

met the study's eligibility criteria: Female, working in banking sector in Türkiye, Actively working in a hybrid environment.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the scales used in the analysis, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were conducted. Additionally, structural equation modeling (SEM) was applied to test the hypothesized relationships between hybrid work, work-life balance, employee well-being and organizational commitment. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic characteristics and key survey responses, while inferential statistical techniques were employed to assess the strength and significance of the relationships between variables.

4. Findings

In this part of the research, descriptive statistics of demographic characteristics and scales, factor and reliability analyses of the scales, relationship analyses between the scales and relationship analyses between the sub-dimensions were given.

4.1. Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Characteristics

According to the descriptive statistics of demographic characteristics, it was observed that the majority of the participants were between the ages of 26 and 45. Specifically, 4% of participants were between 18 and 25 years old, 32% were aged between 26 and 35, while the largest proportion, 45%, belonged to the 36-45 age group. Additionally, 19% of participants were aged 46 and above. A significant portion of the participants were married, accounting for 62% of the sample, while 38% were single. When considering education levels, the majority of participants held a university degree, representing 67% of the sample. Moreover, 25% had obtained a master's degree, while 5% had completed a PhD. A smaller proportion, only 2%, had high school education as their highest level of academic achievement.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics, Factor and Reliability Analyses of the Scales

Table 1. Hybrid Work Environment / Descriptive Statistics, Exploratory Factor and Reliability Analysis Results

Name	Items	Average (X)	Std. deviation	Factor weights	Reliability (α)	Variance explained (%)
Hybrid Work Environment	hw_1	2,86	,59024	,863	,964	68,146
	hw_2	2,91	,55988	,830		
	hw_3	2,88	,59969	,833		
	hw_4	2,87	,63492	,848		
	hw_5	2,97	,62064	,805		
	hw_6	2,87	,59708	,822		
	hw_7	2,92	,55022	,834		
	hw_8	2,87	,61824	,867		
	hw_9	2,90	,60840	,842		
	hw_10	2,89	,59125	,822		
	hw_11	2,93	,59666	,818		
	hw_12	2,91	,59334	,811		
	hw_13	2,91	,60408	,811		
	hw_14	2,87	,57513	,746		

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO): 0,966; Bartlett Test: 0,000

According to Table 1, KMO (0.966) and Bartlett test (lower than 0.001) strongly supported the applicability of factor analysis. The factor weights of all items ranged between 0.746 and 0.867. The high variance explained by a single factor (68.1%), in addition to the high factor loadings indicate that the scale has a unidimensional structure and measures the overall “Hybrid Work Environment” construct. Additionally, this structure aligns with the original scale, further confirming its unidimensional nature. Reliability analysis yielded a value of 0.964, indicating that the scale is highly reliable. The mean values for all items range between 2,86 and 2,97, indicating that participants generally provided responses close to the mid-point of the scale. The highest mean score was observed in hw_5 (2,97), while the lowest mean score was found in hw_1 (2,86).

Model fit indices are statistical measures used to assess how well a structural equation model aligns with the data. When the CMIN/df value is below 5, the model is considered to have an acceptable fit. AGFI and GFI are absolute fit indices, and values close to or above 0.90 indicate a good model fit (Gürbüz, 2024). Comparative fit indices such as NFI, CFI and IFI suggest a strong model fit when they exceed 0.90. The RMSEA value represents the approximate error rate of the model, with a value below 0.08 indicating an acceptable level of model fit (Meydan & Şeşen, 2015). In this study, the evaluation has been conducted based on these criteria.

CMIN/df:2,844; AGFI:,.871; GFI:,.908; NFI:,.946; CFI:,.964; IFI:,.964; RMSEA:,.077

Figure 3. Hybrid Work Environment / Confirmatory Factor Analysis

According to Figure 3, the factor loadings ranged between 0.72 and 0.86, indicating a generally high level. To improve the model's goodness-of-fit, covariances were established between certain latent variables. In terms of the overall model fit, the CMIN/df (2.844) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.871) and GFI (0.908) suggest good overall model

fit, although AGFI is at a borderline acceptable level. The indices NFI (0.946), CFI (0.964), and IFI (0.964) all exceed 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.077) value was below 0.08, further supporting the acceptability of the model fit. All these findings confirm that the factor structure of the "Hybrid Work Environment" scale is validated at an excellent level.

Table 2. Work-Life Balance / Descriptive Statistics, Exploratory Factor and Reliability Analysis Results

Name	Items	Average (X)	Std. deviation	Factor weights				Reliability (α)	Variance explained (%)
				1	2	3	4		
Work-Life Adjustment	wlb_1	4,18	,66906	,677				,842	33,585
	wlb_2	4,30	,60667	,898					
	wlb_3	4,36	,67177	,809					
	wlb_4	4,08	,72946	,675					
	wlb_5	4,01	,77311	,647					
Neglecting Life	wlb_7	3,46	,70263		,787			,877	13,892
	wlb_8	3,62	,96460		,714				
	wlb_9	2,93	,83861		,706				
	wlb_10	3,67	,63310		,800				
	wlb_11	3,94	,91603		,775				
	wlb_12	3,36	,74442		,829				
Taking Time for Yourself	wlb_13	3,41	,77644				,857	,785	12,173
	wlb_14	4,37	,90172				,797		
	wlb_15	3,67	,62286				,744		
	wlb_16	3,52	,69401				,871		
Life Consists of Work	wlb_17	3,62	,65487			,830		,871	8,676
	wlb_18	3,41	,70786			,855			
	wlb_19	3,81	1,00035			,890			
Total scale								,892	

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO): 0,942; Bartlett Test: 0,000; Total variance explained: 68,326

According to Table 2, KMO (0.942) and Bartlett test (lower than 0.001) strongly supported the applicability of factor analysis. Items "wlb_6" and "wlb_20" were removed from the analysis as their factor loadings were below 0.60 and disrupted the factor structure. According to the analysis results, the scale

consists of four sub-dimensions and is reliable (reliability coefficient 0.892). The mean values for all items ranged between 2,94 and 4,37, indicating that participants generally provided responses closer to the upper end of the scale, suggesting a positive perception of work-life balance.

CMIN/df:3,181; AGFI:868; GFI:912; NFI:895; CFI:925; IFI:926; RMSEA:078

Figure 4. Work-Life Balance / Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The items “wlb_14” and “wlb_15” were removed from the analysis as their factor loadings were below 0.60 and negatively affected the model fit (Figure 4). Additionally, the item “wlb_19” was also excluded from the analysis due to its high correlation with other items and a standardized factor loading exceeding the acceptable theoretical limits. As this condition negatively affected the model fit indices, the item was removed to improve overall model adequacy. As a result, the factor loadings in the model ranged between 0.63 and 0.92. To improve the goodness-of-fit values, covariances were established between some latent variables. Regarding

the overall model fit, the CMIN/df (3.181) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.868) and GFI (0.912) suggest a good overall model fit, although AGFI is at a borderline acceptable level. The indices NFI (0.895), CFI (0.925), and IFI (0.926) were very close to and above 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.078) value was below 0.08, supporting the acceptability of the model fit. All these findings indicate that the “Work-Life Balance” scale demonstrates a good level of fit with the data and confirms the existence of four sub-dimensions.

Table 3. Employee Well-being / Descriptive Statistics, Exploratory Factor and Reliability Analysis Results

Name	Items	Average (X)	Std. deviation	Factor weights				Reliability (α)	Variance explained (%)
				1	2	3	4		
Psychological wellbeing	ewb_1	3,57	1,10020		,819			,945	22,529
	ewb_2	3,71	1,03948		,864				
	ewb_3	3,66	1,07289		,816				
	ewb_4	3,71	,95567		,765				
	ewb_5	3,63	1,04612		,822				
	ewb_6	3,62	,96460		,783				
	ewb_7	2,93	1,09767		,795				
	ewb_8	3,97	1,00128		,793				
	ewb_9	3,94	,91603		,828				
	ewb_10	3,47	1,02977		,865				
Social wellbeing	ewb_11	3,08	,66088	,771				,943	34,332
	ewb_12	3,10	,64334	,714					
	ewb_13	3,09	,61888	,843					
	ewb_14	3,06	,60735	,782					
	ewb_15	3,09	,66882	,837					
	ewb_16	3,08	,64112	,745					
	ewb_17	3,10	,65326	,816					
	ewb_18	3,08	,65515	,786					
	ewb_19	3,06	,65816	,737					
Subjective wellbeing	ewb_20	3,62	1,20205				,864	,805	7,734
	ewb_21	4,37	,90172				,687		
	ewb_22	4,00	1,02697				,673		
	ewb_23	3,79	1,00621				,885		
Workplace wellbeing	ewb_24	2,97	,62064			,655		,939	4,102
	ewb_25	2,87	,59708			,679			
	ewb_26	2,92	,55022			,676			
	ewb_27	2,87	,61824			,726			
	ewb_28	2,90	,60840			,731			
	ewb_29	2,89	,59125			,608			
	ewb_30	2,93	,59666			,676			
	ewb_31	2,91	,59334			,651			
Total scale								,815	

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO): 0,913; Bartlett Test: 0,000; Total variance explained: 68,697

According to Table 3, KMO (0.913) and Bartlett test (lower than 0.001) strongly supported the applicability of factor analysis. Results showed that the scale consists of four sub-dimensions and is reliable (reliability coefficient 0.815). The mean values for all items

ranged between 2,87 and 4,37, indicating that participants generally provided responses close to the mid-point to upper end of the scale, suggesting a more positive perception of well-being.

CMIN/df:2,220; AGFI: ,859; GFI: ,907; NFI: ,902; CFI: ,943; IFI: ,944; RMSEA: ,063

Figure 5. Employee Well-being / Confirmatory Factor Analysis

In the confirmatory factor analysis applied to the “Employee Well-being” scale, items “ewb_2”, “ewb_7”, “ewb_21” and “ewb_22” were removed from the analysis as their factor loadings were below 0.60 and negatively affected the model fit. As a result, the factor loadings in the model ranged between 0.73 and 0.94 (Figure 5). To improve the goodness-of-fit values, covariances were established between some latent variables. Regarding the overall model fit, the CMIN/df (2.220) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the

absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.859) and GFI (0.907) suggest a good overall model fit, although AGFI is at a borderline acceptable level. The indices NFI (0.902), CFI (0.943), and IFI (0.944) are all above 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.063) value was below 0.08, further supporting the acceptability of the model fit. All these findings indicate that the “Employee Well-being” scale demonstrates a good level of fit with the data and confirms the existence of four sub-dimensions.

Table 4. Organizational Commitment / Descriptive Statistics, Exploratory Factor and Reliability Analysis Results

Name	Items	Average (X)	Std. deviation	Factor weights			Reliability (α)	Variance explained (%)
				1	2	3		
Affective Commitment	oc_1	2,89	,59125		,698		,923	9,583
	oc_2	2,93	,59666		,650			
	oc_3	2,91	,59334		,808			
	oc_4	2,91	,60408		,760			
	oc_5	2,87	,57513		,574			
	oc_6	2,92	,64267		,728			

Continuance Commitment	oc_7	2,77	,63725	,618	,890	5,681
	oc_8	2,85	,65938	,776		
	oc_9	2,76	,62987	,726		
	oc_10	2,84	,63300	,683		
	oc_11	2,87	,67779	,732		
	oc_12	2,85	,61544	,691		
Normative Commitment	oc_13	3,08	,66489	,732	,965	51,050
	oc_14	3,13	,63232	,791		
	oc_15	3,03	,60459	,643		
	oc_16	3,09	,66882	,691		
	oc_17	3,02	,62064	,764		
		3,08	,65108	,808		
Total scale					,953	

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO): 0,945; Bartlett Test: 0,000; Total variance explained: 66,314

According to Table 4, KMO (0.945) and Bartlett test (lower than 0.001) strongly supported the applicability of factor analysis. Results indicated that the scale consists of three sub-dimensions and is highly reliable (reliability coefficient 0.953). The mean values

for all items ranged between 2,77 and 3,13, indicating that participants generally provided responses around the mid-point of the scale, suggesting a neutral stance on organizational commitment.

CMIN/df:2,375; AGFI: ,876; GFI: ,904; NFI: ,915; CFI: ,948; IFI: ,949; RMSEA: ,066

Figure 6. Organizational Commitment / Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The factor loadings ranged between 0.65 and 0.84, indicating a generally high level (Figure 6). Regarding the overall model fit, the CMIN/df (2.375) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.876) and GFI (0.904) suggest a good overall model fit, although AGFI is at a borderline acceptable level. The indices

NFI (0.915), CFI (0.948) and IFI (0.949) all exceed 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.066) value was below 0.08, further supporting the acceptability of the model fit. All these findings indicate that the “Organizational Commitment” scale demonstrates a good level of fit with the data and confirms the existence of three sub-dimensions.

4.2. Relationship Analyses Between the Scales

Figure 7. The Effect of Hybrid Work Environments on Organizational Commitment / Structural Equation Model (SEM)

As seen in Figure 7, covariances were determined between some latent variables to improve the goodness of fit values. When examining the model fit indices, the CMIN/df (2.549) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.889) and GFI (0.906) suggest a good overall model fit. The indices NFI (0.902), CFI (0.935) and IFI (0.940) all exceed 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.068) value was below 0.08, further supporting the acceptability of the model fit. Based on all these values, it can be concluded that the structural model falls within acceptable limits, confirming the validity of the model.

When examining the relationship between hybrid work environment and organizational commitment, the standardized regression coefficient ($\beta = 0.529$, $p < 0.001$) was found to be positive and statistically significant. This positive relationship indicates that as the hybrid work increases, the level of organizational commitment also increases. Evaluating the explanatory power of the model, it was observed that the independent latent variable, hybrid work environment explains 60.2% of the variance in the dependent latent variable organizational commitment ($R^2 = 0.602$). All these findings suggest that the hybrid work environment plays a significant role in enhancing organizational commitment levels.

Figure 8. Employee Well-being, Work-Life Balance, Hybrid Work Environments and Organizational Commitment Scales / Structural Equation Model (SEM) and Model Fit Criteria

Path analysis results and goodness-of-fit values for hybrid work environment, organizational commitment, employee well-being and work-life balance are presented above Figure 8. To improve the goodness-of-fit values, covariances were established between some latent variables. When examining the model fit indices, the CMIN/df (2.307) value was below 5, indicating an acceptable model fit. Among the absolute fit indices, AGFI (0.869) and GFI (0.901) suggest a good overall model fit, although AGFI is

at a borderline acceptable level. The indices NFI (0.909), CFI (0.908), and IFI (0.911) all exceed 0.90, indicating a strong model fit. Additionally, the RMSEA (0.074) value was below 0.08, further supporting the acceptability of the model fit. Based on all these values, it can be concluded that the structural model falls within acceptable limits, confirming the validity of the model. Structural equation model results are presented in Table 5:

Table 5. Model Pathways

Dependent		Independent	St. β	St. Er	R ²	p	Hypotheses	Hypotheses results
EWB	←	HW	,741	,179	,549	***	H3	Accepted
WLB	←	HW	-,682	,106	,466	***	H1	Accepted
OC	←	EWB	,089	,120	,311	,021	H4	Accepted
OC	←	WLB	-,181	,196		,042	H2	Accepted
OC	←	HW	,350	,261		,048	H5	Accepted

***p<0,001

The effect of the Hybrid Work Environment (HW) on Employee Well-being (EWB) ($\beta = 0.741, p < 0.001$) was positive, strong and statistically significant (therefore H3 is accepted). This result indicates that employees' well-being significantly improves in a hybrid work environment. 54.9% of the variance in Employee Well-being is explained by the Hybrid Work Environment ($R^2 = 0.549$). This finding suggests that hybrid work substantially supports employee well-being.

On the other hand, the effect of the Hybrid Work Environment (HW) on Work-Life Balance (WLB) is negative, strong and statistically significant ($\beta = -0.682, p < 0.001$) (therefore H1 is accepted). 46.6% of the variance in Work-Life Balance is explained by the Hybrid Work Environment ($R^2 = 0.466$). This indicates that the hybrid work environment may have a negative impact on work-life balance, making it difficult for employees to establish clear boundaries between their work and personal lives.

When examining the effects on Organizational Commitment (OC), the impact of Employee Well-being on Organizational Commitment was positive, statistically significant, but relatively weak ($\beta = 0.089, p = 0.021$). The relationship between Work-Life Balance and Organizational Commitment was negative and significant ($\beta = -0.181, p = 0.042$). As work-life balance improves, employees' commitment to their organization may decrease. Therefore, H4 and H2 were accepted.

The direct effect of the Hybrid Work Environment on Organizational Commitment is positive, statistically significant, but moderate in strength ($\beta = 0.350, p = 0.048$) (therefore H5 is accepted). This result indicates that while the hybrid work environment can enhance employees' commitment, its effect is limited. The indirect and mediating effects of the Hybrid Work Environment on Organizational Commitment are presented in the following Table 6:

Table 6. Mediation Analysis Results

	St. Indirect effect (β)	Bootstrap (Lower Bounds/Upper Bounds) %95 Confidence Interval	Hypotheses	Hypotheses results
OC ← EWB ← HW	,741	,649/, 846	H7	Accepted
OC ← WLB ← HW	-,682	-,799/-,594	H6	Accepted

Note: Bootstrap sample of 5,000

The mediation analysis conducted in this study aligns with the four-step approach proposed by Baron and Kenny (1986), which remains a foundational method in testing indirect effects between variables. According to their framework, a variable is considered a mediator if the following conditions are met: (1) the independent variable significantly affects the dependent variable; (2) the independent variable significantly affects the mediator; (3) the mediator significantly affects the dependent variable while controlling for the independent variable; and (4) the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable is reduced when the mediator is included in the model. In this research, the hybrid work environment was shown to significantly influence both mediators, employee well-being and work-life balance, as well as the dependent variable, organizational commitment. Furthermore, when the mediators were included in the model both mediators had significant indirect effects, as confirmed by bootstrapping analysis. These results support the presence of partial mediation and validate the theoretical assumptions grounded in Baron and Kenny's approach.

In fact, the above Table 6 presents indirect effects (β) of Hybrid Work (HW) on Organizational Commitment (OC) through two mediating variables: Employee Well-being (EWB) and Work-Life Balance

(WLB). The results indicate that Hybrid Work Environment (HW) has a significant indirect effect on Organizational Commitment (OC) through Employee Well-being (EWB). The standardized indirect effect ($\beta = 0.741$) demonstrates a strong positive impact, suggesting that employees who experience improved well-being in a hybrid work environment are more likely to feel committed to their organization. The bootstrap confidence interval (95% CI: [0.649, 0.846]) does not include zero, confirming the statistical significance of this indirect effect. Therefore, H7 was accepted, supporting the idea that hybrid work positively influences organizational commitment by enhancing employee well-being.

On the other hand, the analysis also revealed a significant negative indirect effect of Hybrid Work Environment (HW) on Organizational Commitment through Work-Life Balance (WLB). The standardized indirect effect ($\beta = -0.682$) indicated that hybrid work negatively impacts work-life balance, which in turn reduces employees' commitment to their organization. The bootstrap confidence interval (95% CI: [-0.799, -0.594]) does not include zero, confirming that this indirect effect is statistically significant. As a result, H6 was accepted, indicating that the hybrid work environment weakens work-life balance, which subsequently leads to a decline in organizational commitment.

These findings highlight the dual nature of hybrid work, showing that while it enhances employee well-being and contributes positively to commitment, it negatively affects work-life balance, which in turn reduces organizational commitment. Orga-

nizations should carefully evaluate their hybrid work policies, ensuring that they optimize employee well-being while minimizing disruptions to work-life balance to sustain organizational commitment.

4.3. Relationship Analyses Between the Sub-Dimensions

Table 7. Regression Analysis Results

Dependent		Independent	β	p
Affective Commitment	←	Hybrid Work	,369	< ,001
Continuance Commitment	←	Hybrid Work	,377	< ,001
Normative Commitment	←	Hybrid Work	,493	< ,001
Psychological Well-being	←	Hybrid Work	,622	< ,001
Social Well-being	←	Hybrid Work	,485	< ,001
Subjective Well-being	←	Hybrid Work	,522	< ,001
Workplace Well-being	←	Hybrid Work	,538	< ,001
Work-life Adjustment	←	Hybrid Work	-,480	< ,001
Neglecting Life	←	Hybrid Work	-,327	< ,001
Taking Time for Yourself	←	Hybrid Work	-,470	< ,001
Life Consists of Work	←	Hybrid Work	-,484	< ,001
Affective Commitment	←	Workplace Well-being	,317	,003
Continuance Commitment	←	Workplace Well-being	,335	,002
Normative Commitment	←	Social Well-being	,389	< ,001
Continuance Commitment	←	Life Consists of Work	-,221	,039

Regression analysis results show that the hybrid working model has statistically significant effects on all sub-dimensions (Table 7). These results mean that hybrid working increases the moral responsibility or obligation of employees towards the organization and strengthens the emotional commitment and the perception of the obligation to continue working. Based on Table 7, it can also be said that hybrid working may lead to blurring of boundaries and work dominating private life.

5. Discussion, Model Proposal and Conclusion

The results demonstrate that the hybrid work environment has a strong, positive effect on well-being ($\beta = 0.741$, $p < 0.001$). This finding supports previous research (Mortensen & Haas, 2021; Sun et al., 2025) and aligns with the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). This positive effect, according to literature, depends on the level of resources provided by organizations (da Silva et al., 2022). However, negative impact of hybrid work on work-life balance was also found in this study ($\beta = -0.682$, $p < 0.001$). This showed that rather than

reducing work-life conflict, hybrid work, in Türkiye setting, worsen the work-life balance of the female employees. This finding is consistent with Work-Family Conflict Theory (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985), which suggests that role conflicts between work and personal life negatively impact professional engagement and well-being. Prior research also identifies the "always-on" culture as a major downside of hybrid work, as employees experience heightened expectations for availability, leading to increased stress and difficulty maintaining personal boundaries (Selvaraju, 2024). Supporting this, Yosunkaya (2023) found that while a significant proportion of hybrid employees expressed satisfaction with this work model, 66% reported concerns about the dissolution of clear working hours, reinforcing the notion that work-life balance remains a major area of concern. This aligns with observations in collectivist and high-context cultures, such as Türkiye, where strong family ties and social expectations intensify the challenges of maintaining work-life balance. The cultural emphasis on caregiving roles for women may further exacerbate these difficulties, suggesting that hybrid work models require careful adaptation to fit the socio-cultural fabric of such societies.

This study further reveals that while employee well-being positively influences organizational commitment ($\beta = 0.089$, $p = 0.021$), this relationship is relatively weak. This suggests that while well-being contributes to commitment, it is not the primary driver since commitment may be influenced by other factors such as job security and career progression (Saritha & Akthar, 2024). Nevertheless, the moderate effect of hybrid work on organizational commitment ($\beta = 0.350$, $p = 0.048$) supports prior research indicating that flexible work arrangements can enhance commitment when employees perceive them as beneficial for professionals (Vidya Sri & Vasantha, 2024). This pattern aligns closely with findings reported in Western contexts, where hybrid work often strengthens organizational commitment due to increased autonomy and work flexibility, which are highly valued in individualistic and low power distance cultures. However, the relatively weak influence of well-being on commitment observed in this study may reflect the specific cultural characteristics of Türkiye, where hierarchical relationships, job security, and career progression are more central to organizational commitment. In high power distance cultures like Türkiye, employees may prioritize stability and managerial recognition over personal well-being as primary drivers of commitment, thus explaining the limited role well-being plays in fostering commitment in this context.

An unexpected yet significant result was found as the negative relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment ($\beta = -0.181$, $p = 0.042$). This contradicts much of the existing literature, which generally suggests that a better work-life balance raises higher engagement and retention. A possible explanation is that as employees achieve a better work-life balance, they may feel less dependent on their organizations and thus less committed (Marozva & Pelser, 2025). This shift in career priorities could lead female employees who achieve sustainable work-life balance to prioritize personal fulfillment over long-term loyalty to an organization (Bhargavi, 2025). Another plausible interpretation, as suggested by Marozva & Pelser (2025), is that greater autonomy in hybrid settings may reduce employees' sense of belonging, potentially weakening their long-term organizational commitment. Similar patterns have been observed in other Asian cultural contexts, further emphasizing the culturally contingent nature of hybrid work outcomes. For example, in India, recent research has highlighted both the benefits and challenges associated with hybrid work arrangements. Vidya Sri and Vasantha (2024) found that hybrid and remote working models positively influence employees' work-life balance by providing greater flexibility. However, the same study revealed that these models generate uncertainty regarding career advancement and organizational commitment, largely due to the cultural importan-

ce placed on hierarchical visibility and face-to-face interactions within the Indian workplace. Supporting this view, Rani and Rakesh (2024) demonstrated that while hybrid work enhances the well-being of female employees in India, concerns surrounding reduced leadership visibility and limited career progression persist, reflecting the influence of gender roles and organizational hierarchies in high power distance cultures. In China, similar findings have emerged. Qi et al. (2021) reported that hybrid work environments strengthen organizational commitment when clear communication and managerial support are present, which aligns with China's hierarchical cultural structure. However, in the absence of these support systems, employees experience increased stress due to heightened uncertainty, a common characteristic of high uncertainty avoidance cultures. Moreover, Liu and Sutunyarak (2025) highlighted that while flexible working schedules improve work-life balance among Chinese employees, the social isolation resulting from reduced physical interaction negatively affects psychological well-being, illustrating the importance of collective harmony in Chinese society. A comparable situation exists in Indonesia, where cultural values rooted in collectivism influence the reception of hybrid work models. Irawanto et al. (2021) found that while flexible work arrangements contribute positively to work-life balance, the lack of regular in-person interactions undermines organizational commitment, as strong group cohesion and face-to-face engagement remain central to Indonesian workplace culture. Furthermore, Irawanto et al. (2021) reported that hybrid work presents specific challenges for female employees in Indonesia, particularly in managing family responsibilities alongside professional duties, leading to difficulties in maintaining work-life balance.

These findings collectively emphasize the dual nature of hybrid work: while it enhances employee well-being and contributes positively to organizational commitment, it simultaneously disrupts work-life balance, which in turn can diminish commitment levels. This underscores the importance of strategic hybrid work policies that not only promote well-being but also actively prevent work-life imbalances from eroding organizational loyalty. Organizations must establish clear boundaries, develop leadership visibility programs, and provide structured support mechanisms to ensure that hybrid work serves as an enabler rather than a disruptor of long-term workforce engagement. Findings also clearly demonstrated that in different cultures, hybrid work may have different effects. In collectivist and high-power distance cultures like Türkiye, organizational commitment often stems from hierarchical relationships, social obligations, and economic security rather than solely from personal well-being or work-life balance. These insights reinforce the argument that hybrid work models should not be universally applied with-

hout consideration of cultural contexts. Instead, they should be adapted to align with the social expectations, organizational structures, and cultural norms of the regions in which they are implemented.

In addition to considering cultural perspective, job resources should also be improved. In the literature it was stated that hybrid work is a different working model than remote work, and since employees work at home and sometimes in the office, they mostly have no special work area where they can focus on their work-related responsibilities in their homes (Gorjifard & Crawford, 2021). This situation reveals that women, particularly those who have motherhood or home-related responsibilities, often find themselves managing their work-related responsibilities concurrently with home-related tasks. This situation can reduce both the focus and motivation of women and their desire to continue working. Therefore, it is important for organizations to support their employees. This includes providing ongoing training on ef-

fective work from home practices, raising awareness of the potential challenges of these arrangements, and offering clear guidance on how to address the problems they may encounter in this working system through practical solutions. In this respect, it can be argued that if organizations increase supportive job resources such as training programs, more ergonomic work areas for women in the homes or better technological opportunities and make these resources accessible to female employees, they can create a female employee base with higher commitment.

In fact, based on the results it can be said that conflict which occurs through work-family balance can be mitigated by increasing job resources and considering cultural differences. This can be used as a formula for achieving organizational commitment among the women who work in hybrid working system. Based on this, following model (Figure 9) that is build on the culture, job demand and job resources can be offered:

Figure 9. Conceptual Model Proposal

The proposed conceptual model integrates hybrid work arrangements with the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) framework and embeds Hofstede’s cultural dimensions as key moderators shaping the perception and outcomes of these work structures. While the JD-R model suggests that job demands and job resources directly affect employee well-being, work-life balance, and ultimately organizational commitment, this framework posits that these relationships are significantly influenced by cultural context. In fact, when considering western culture, autonomy and flexibility are generally perceived as positive job resources. It is because, employees of western culture are familiar with making independent decisions and managing their own schedules due to their culture’s features such as low power distance, high individualism, and low uncertainty avoidance. Nevertheless, in eastern cultures, these same elements may be seen as job demands rather than resources. In cultures like Türkiye, autonomy possib-

ly will no longer function as a resource but rather it will be understood as a demand. It is because, in high-power distance cultures employees are more comfortable receiving direct instructions from their superiors and thus, giving them a space for authorization in their decisions understood as increased demand. In fact, when autonomy is assigned to the employees without structured guidance, it can create ambiguity and stress. Therefore, flexibility in hybrid work settings can be perceived as an additional source of uncertainty rather than a benefit. Similarly, in collectivist cultures like Türkiye, face-to-face interactions, group organization, and shared decision-making are essential parts of working. Hybrid work reduces physical presence and increases remote interactions. In fact, it weakens social connections, decreases trust, and disrupts team dynamics. As a result, employees may experience decreased well-being and damaged work-life balance, specifically when organizational support systems are in-

sufficient to close these gaps. Nevertheless, cultural factors can also lessen these negative effects under certain conditions. For instance, the femininity dimension can enhance the perception of job resources, even in more hierarchical cultures. In cultures where femininity is stronger, supportive leadership, structured policies, and psychological safety can counterbalance the stress induced by high demands while increasing the well-being and organizational commitment.

This framework contributes to the literature by demonstrating that cultural dimensions actively moderate the effects of hybrid work, leading to varied psychological and organizational outcomes across different regions. Such insights emphasize the importance of adapting hybrid work policies to cultural contexts to ensure that intended benefits, such as improved well-being, work-life balance, and organizational commitment, are realized. This is also important from the perspective of sustainability as from a sustainability perspective, it is not enough for women to simply enter the workforce through hybrid work arrangements. Indeed, what truly matters and what truly provides a positive impact on sustainable development is ensuring their long-term engagement in professional life. A strong sense of commitment supports career continuity, reinforces professional identity, and lowers the likelihood of employees leaving their positions, particularly among women.

Despite its contributions, the study has certain limitations. The most significant limitation relates to the sample selection process. Due to the lack of official records identifying the number of hybrid workers in Türkiye, the study relied on earlier studies' sampling process which can limit the generalizability of the results. Efforts were made to mitigate this by reaching as many participants as possible, but future research should aim to employ more robust sampling strategies, including representative samples across various sectors and industries. For future research, comparative studies across different cultural contexts are recommended to further explore how cultural values influence the perception and outcomes of hybrid work.

Declaration:

Ethics committee approval for the research was obtained by the Istanbul Kent University, Social and Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee with the decision dated 03.01.2025 and meeting number 2025/01.

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